

AN INTERACTIVE GRAPHICS EDITOR WITH INTEGRATED DATA DICTIONARY FOR *IDEF*₀ STRUCTURED ANALYSIS DIAGRAMS

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Abstract

Most of the commercially available structured analysis tools are based on data flow diagrams. However, many Government agencies, from the Air Force Materials Laboratory to the Strategic Defense Initiative Office depend on *IDEF*₀ diagrams, a derivative of SofTech's Structured Analysis and Design Technique (SADT¹). This paper describes *SAtool*, a graphics *IDEF*₀ editor for a SUN workstation.

An extension of the original *IDEF*₀ definition is a data dictionary. Entries are defined for both activities and data items, and mapped into a relational database management system (DBMS). A data manager handles checking data out of the centralized DBMS in a format useable by the graphics editor and updating the appropriate relations when the data is checked back in. The data manager was developed in a generic format to support other software development tools.

The editor and data manager, as part of the Air Force Institute of Technology's *System 690* software development system, were used in the development of a distributed mail system. User acceptance of the tool was measured through the use of a user survey. Results of this survey, as well as a description of the editor and data manager, are presented in the paper.

1 Introduction

System 690 is the name given to the software development environment under development at the Air Force Institute of Technology's Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering. The goal of *System 690* is to provide an integrated system in which a designer could sit down at a workstation, download the necessary data from a central database, work on a portion of the design, and when finished, upload the modified data back to the database. This data, stored in a comprehensive, centralized database, would support a system which could share data between tools and provide the means to document a software project throughout its entire life cycle.

System 690 is based on a set of integrated workstation tools and a central database to support a specific design methodology. In its current implementation, *System 690*

supports a classical process-oriented lifecycle based on the ideas in Dod Standard 2167. A standard "waterfall" model is followed, consisting of a Requirements Analysis phase, a Design phase, an Implementation & Testing phase, and a Maintenance phase. Each phase is supported by database consisting of specific *data dictionary* entries.

This paper describes a graphics tool developed to support the Requirements Analysis phase and the integration of that tool with a centralized relational database management system. Some results of analysis of user satisfaction with this tool are also presented. This paper describes the integration of these two techniques into a computer automated tool *SAtool* for the purpose of improving the software requirements analyst's productivity. This productivity increase is possible for two significant reasons. First, several pieces of information are needed for both an SA diagram and the corresponding data dictionary entries. The integration of the two methods eliminates significant duplication of effort to enter the information. Second, the analyst is freed from much of the effort needed to create the diagram manually by using a tool tailored for this specific purpose. *SAtool* executes on a SUN workstation and transfers data dictionary information over a TCP/IP local area network (LAN) and through a data manager to a central relational database management system on a Unix-based Vax computer.

2 Requirements Analysis Methodology

The requirements analysis phase of the software life cycle is an important one. *System 690* has established an analysis methodology for this phase of the software life cycle that consists of using structured analysis (SA) diagrams and a data dictionary. This section describes each of the components.

2.1 SA Diagrams

The SA diagrams use a graphical language that is derived from the Structured Analysis and Design Technique

¹SADT is a registered trademark of SofTech, Inc

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(SADT) (SADT is a trademark of SofTech, Inc.), and are accompanied by facing page text to assist in the understanding of the diagram. Rectangular boxes and arrows are the primary graphical constructs used in an SADT diagram. The boxes represent the decomposition of the functions of the system being analyzed. The arrows are used to describe how the boxes interface between each other on the diagram. The graphical language consists of English text to label the diagram and 40 graphical constructs to describe relationships [1].

SofTech proposed that the SADT methodology could be applied to many types of problems in addition to software requirements analysis [2]. The U.S. Air Force Program for Integrated Computer Aided Manufacturing (ICAM) adopted a version of SADT from SofTech and called it ICAM Definition Method Zero or *IDEF₀*. Now the Air Force uses this similarly structured methodology to improve the communication of people who use computers to increase manufacturing productivity.

System 690 uses the *IDEF₀* syntax to support the requirements analysis phase of the software development life-cycle. A example of an *IDEF₀* diagram as produced by *SAtool* is shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Data Dictionary

The purpose of a data dictionary is to manage and document data. According to Lefkovits (Lefkovits, 1977), using data dictionaries provides many benefits including: reduction of administrative effort, reduction of data redundancy, and reduction of system development costs. Regarding software requirements analysis, Leong-Hong and Plagman suggested that data dictionaries are an excellent vehicle for maintaining documentation. Furthermore, they recommended that the data dictionary system for producing documentation be automated to reduce the monotony of the task. [3].

In System 690, a data dictionary is established for the Requirements Analysis, Design, and Implementation phases of the software life cycle. Each of these phases consists of a set of action entities and a set of object entities for a total of six types of data dictionary entries. Figure 2 shows a sample data dictionary entry.

The data dictionary entries, as can be seen from Figure 2, are designed to be readable by human analysts. The corresponding relational database consists of a number of third-normal form relations. (Figure 3 shows the schema for the design phase object entity). The data dictionary database contains the schema for all six data dictionary entries, and is implemented using the Ingres relational DBMS under the Unix operating system on a VAX 11/785.

Figure 1: Example *IDEF₀* Diagram

NAME: mess_parts
 PROJECT: NETOS-ISO
 TYPE: PARAMETER
 DESCRIPTION: Decomposed message parameters.
 DATA TYPE: C structure or PASCAL record.
 MIN VALUE: None
 MAX VALUE: None
 RANGE OF VALUES: None
 VALUES: None
 PART OF: None
 COMPOSITION:
 SRC
 DST
 QTY
 Buffer
 ALIAS: Message Parts
 WHERE USED: Passed to Flush Buffer.
 COMMENT: Part of existing library.
 REFERENCE: MSG_PARTS
 REFERENCE TYPE: SADT
 VERSION: 1.2
 VERSION CHANGES: Component USE added
 DATE: 11/05/85
 AUTHOR: T. C. Hartrum
 CALLING PROCESS: Process Message
 PROCESS CALLED: Decompose_Message
 DIRECTION: up
 I/O PARAMETER NAME: parts_list

Figure 2: Sample Design Phase Object Entity Dictionary Entry [4]

parameter			
project	c12		
paname	c25		
datatype	c25		
low	c15		
hi	c15		
span	c60		
status	c1		
padesc			
project	c12		
paname	c25		
line	i2		
description	c60		
paalias			
project	c12		
paname	c25		
aliasname	c25		
comment	c60		
whereused	c25		
pahistory			
project	c12		
paname	c25		
version	c10		
date	c8		
author	c20		
comment	c60		
		papassed	
		project	c12
		paname	c25
		prcalling	c25
		prcalled	c25
		direction	c4
		iopaname	c25
		pavalueset	
		project	c12
		paname	c25
		value	c15
		pahierarchy	
		project	c12
		hipaname	c25
		lopaname	c25
		paref	
		project	c12
		paname	c25
		reference	c60
		reftype	c25

Figure 3: Database Schema for the Design Phase Object Entity [5]

3 SAtool, an Interactive Graphics Editor

3.1 Requirements Definition

Requirements for this tool were based on previous research at AFIT. A prototype tool to integrate SA diagrams and data dictionaries was built at AFIT in 1986. This prototype implemented a small subset of the entire SA language syntax used by SADT and *IDEF₀*. To extend this prototype effort, it was necessary to examine the SADT and *IDEF₀* graphic syntaxes and identify a necessary and sufficient language for implementation of this tool.

The prototype, as well as this tool, were required to carefully consider the human/computer interface aspect of the tool because of the interactive nature of the program. Specifically, the following rules for developing human/computer interfaces were considered in its design [6]:

1. Keep the user motivated.

2. Break the input process into parts to achieve "psychological closure."
3. Provide positive feedback to the user.
4. Minimize memorization required by the user.
5. Provide a visually pleasing display on the screen.
6. Minimize the response time of the tool.

Finally, part of the tool's function was to provide hard-copy outputs of the various products maintained by the tool. Therefore, it was required that the tool implement a means to produce the *IDEF₀* diagram, the accompanying facing page text, and the data dictionaries generated by the tool.

3.2 Description of the Tool

SAtool was designed to run on SUN workstations due to their availability. Each SUN has a large display monitor to accommodate an uncluttered user interface, and a mouse input device for manipulating the graphical constructs of the *IDEF₀* diagram. In addition, all the SUN workstations are tied to the AFIT computer network, important for transporting the data dictionary information to the central computer. Based on the availability of the SunView package and the desire to reuse certain software modules from the prototype, it was decided to proceed with the SunView package. The tool was implemented in C because SunView supports this language.

The design of an acceptable human/computer interface was a primary task in this effort. The screen layout consists of five areas or windows as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: SAtool Screen Layout

These are the Input Window, the Message Window, the Selection Window, the Diagram Window, and the Data Dictionary Window. The Input Window is where the user enters all text labels for the diagram. In the Message Window, the user receives instructions, feedback, and help messages. The Selection Window provides a mechanism for choosing one of four menus of actions needed to build an *IDEF0* diagram and data dictionaries. The Diagram Window shows the current diagram and the Data Dictionary Window is where data dictionary information not derived from the diagram is entered by the user.

A menu-system was selected because it solved several rules for a good user interface. The menu selections are grouped according to the major function they provide: editing a diagram, editing a data dictionary, displaying facing page text, saving the diagram, or executing system functions (*e.g.* changing the working directory). Within each grouping, the menu selections are structured in a hierarchical manner that matches the functional decomposition of the tool.

3.3 Data Files

The tool is capable of producing five data files, two that save raw data (graphics and data dictionary information) and three that save output products of the tool. Each file has a unique file extension.

The first two files save the raw data when the "save" menu option is selected. The first one contains graphics information and is labeled with a ".gph" extension. The second contains the data dictionary information in a format readable by the database's data management system. This file is labeled with a ".dbs" extension. The remaining three files are generated at the option of the user. The facing page text for a diagram is stored in an ASCII file with a ".fpt" extension. The data dictionaries associated with a diagram may be saved in a file with a ".dd" extension appended to the file name. These can be printed on any standard line printer. Finally, a copy of the diagram on the screen may be saved in a file with a ".dmp" extension which is in a SUN rasterfile format and must be printed by a printer that supports this format.

4 The Data Manager

4.1 Objective

Although this paper specifically discusses the Requirements Analysis tool *SAtool*, the objective of the *data manager* is to integrate a set of heterogeneous software engineering tools that run on a wide variety of workstations by designing and implementing a common database interface between the tools and a central relational database. This interface is implemented using a standard data file to trans-

fer data between the tools and a data manager which performs all database transactions. A primary design consideration was for the interface to support the incorporation of new tools into System 690.

The following describes how the data manager would be used in a typical analysis session using *SAtool* from a remote workstation. The workstation requests a set of data entities from the database. Ideally, this should be done via the tool itself, as shown in Figure 5, but in the current implementation of *SAtool* the user remotely logs on to the central host and interactively accesses the data manager directly, as shown in Figure 6.

On receipt of the request, the data manager retrieves the data and provides this data back to the requestor in a standard data file. When retrieving the data, the data manager provides session control to maintain database integrity by recording information about the logged-out data in its own database relations. When the desired changes have been made to the data by the analyst, the tool (user) which checked-out the data requests to update the database. The data manager then uses the standard data file, containing any changes made by the tool, and the session information previously generated during the retrieval to coordinate and perform the database updates. After the data is successfully written back to the database, the session is terminated.

4.2 Data Manager Description

The data manager performs many tasks, but its basic function is to retrieve data from and write data to a relational database using the standard data file. The data manager also provides an interface which allows tools and users to specify the transactions to be performed. Finally, it provides session control to protect database integrity.

Much of the data manager's efforts are based on its own database relations. The primary components used are the *tool data definition table* and the *tool description table*. These tables permit the generic classification of the

Figure 5: Data Manager as Controlled by the Tool

Figure 6: Data Manager Interactively Controlled

entities used by a tool. The *tool data definition table* supports the retrieval of data dictionary entries, formatting the retrieved data into the standard file format, and updating the database. This table provides all the information necessary to retrieve or update a data element and it contains the information necessary to read and write the standard data file. A data definition table must be created for each data entity type used by a tool. Each table has a unique relation name and is tool, phase, and type specific. The use of multiple relations localizes the impact of tool changes and supports the requirement to easily incorporate new tools into System 690. To add a new tool, the only requirement is for the appropriate tool data definition table(s) be created. The *tool description table* describes a tool and its data needs to the data manager, and is used for transaction request verification and database retrievals and updates. There is a tool description table entry for each phase and type of data entity used by a tool. This is required to identify the specific data definition table relation describing the requested data dictionary entry. This table, in conjunction with the data definition table, allows the data manager to identify the standard data file requirements for any System 690 tool.

4.3 Tool/User Interface

The tool/user interface is provided to allow a tool or user to specify to the data manager the type of transaction to perform, and to provide the transaction's results to the tool or user. The interface supports both interactive user requests (Figure 6) and direct tool requests (Figure 5). This is done by means of the *tool data request*, a file that contains the information needed by the data manager to perform all of its database transactions. This includes informing the data manager of the action it is to take. The transactions supported by the data manager are data retrievals, updates, deletions, and session aborts. The *data delete* function is provided to allow a user to delete specified entities without having to retrieve them for update by a remote workstation tool. The *session abort* function was included

to provide an easy means to abort an old or corrupted session, allowing data entities identified as "checked-out" to be made available for other users. All transaction results are reported back to the tool/user through the use of a results file. The results file contains the list of successfully performed transactions. In the case of an error, the cause and error recovery results are placed in the results file.

4.4 Session Control

Session control provides the data manager's librarian function. During retrievals, the data manager determines the status of all requested data entities and generates the session control information. During updates, the data manager uses this information to perform transaction verification to insure that only the permitted modifications have been requested. This session information is maintained in two tables, session entity table and session identification table. The *session entity table* tracks each entity used in a session, its type, and update status. The *session identification table* maintains the status of a session, describes the type of data used in a session, and identifies the session's owner and tool being used. This table supports the data manager update function in verifying session update requests and provides the database administrator an easy way to identify session owners.

4.5 Standard Data File

The standard data file is the means used by the data manager to transfer data between System 690 tools and the common database. It provides a standard file structure for all tools to use in interfacing with the data manager. The file is the interface and therefore must contain not only the requested tool data, but also provide control information to the tool and data manager by describing the contents of the file. The standard data file consists of two components. The *file description header* provides the information necessary to inform a tool and the data manager what the contents and structure of the file are. The *data portion* of the standard data file consists of one or more *data entity entries*, each composed of all the data elements necessary to satisfy a data dictionary entry. The ability to describe a data element allows the element records in a file to be ordered to satisfy a tool's specific data requirements.

5 System Evaluation

5.1 SAtool

SAtool was made available to two graduate level software engineering classes for use and evaluation. Thirty-three students were assigned to create one diagram using the tool and to complete a quantitative evaluation of the tool

based on that experience. On a scale from -1.00 (maximally dissatisfied) to +1.00 (maximally satisfied), the user scores averaged 0.295. The scores ranged from -0.182 to .682 with a standard deviation from the mean of 0.294. On the average, the evaluators used the tool about 138 minutes before completing the evaluation.

5.2 Data Manager

To evaluate the data manager and standard data file implementation, two tools, an existing data dictionary editor and *SAtool* were modified to interface with the standard data file. Both tools were able to successfully use the common interface and access the central database. The most important result of this integration was the ease in which the tools were modified to support the interface. The programmers modifying the tools found the standard data file to support the integration very well and did not require extensive programming effort to incorporate its use with their tools.

6 Summary and Conclusions

This paper has described the design and integration of *SAtool*, an interactive *IDEF₀* diagram graphics editor that integrates data dictionary information. The resulting data dictionary files are compatible with the System 690 *data manager*, a flexible interface which integrates software development tools with a commercial relational database management system.

The objective of *SAtool* to improve the requirements analyst's productivity was demonstrated through the quantitative assessment of a group of graduate students who used the tool to create *IDEF₀* diagrams. The data manager's goal of easily supporting the integration of new tools was demonstrating by successfully integrating two tools currently in use in System 690.

The development of *SAtool* and the data manager provide a big step forward in the development of the System 690 integrated software development environment.

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